

On the Order-theoretic Cantor Theorem

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Abstract

In 2000, Granas and Horvath published an order-theoretic version of the Cantor theorem based on the interplay of the notions of partial order and of completeness. This result gave a unified and simplified account to a long list of results related to the Bishop-Phelps theorem. In the present article, we obtain characterizations of their Cantor type theorem, that is, its equivalent formulations to maximality theorem, various types of collectively fixed point theorems and collectively stationary point theorems. We are based on our 2023 Metatheorem in the ordered fixed point theory and the Brøndsted-Jachymski principle recently due to ourselves.

Keywords: Cantor theorem, fixed point theorem, pre-order, metric space, fixed point, stationary point, maximal element.

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1. Introduction

The well-known Cantor intersection theorem states: If $\{F_n\}_{n \in \mathbb{N}}$ is a decreasing sequence of nonempty closed sets in a complete metric space (X, d) such that $\inf_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \text{diam } F_n = 0$, then $\bigcap_{n \in \mathbb{N}} F_n \neq \emptyset$.

In 2000, Granas-Horvath [14] presented an order-theoretic version of the Cantor theorem based on the interplay of the notions of partial order and of completeness. This result was shown to give a unified and simplified account to a long list of results related to the Bishop-Phelps theorem [2] in 1963; see Dugundji-Granas [10,13].

Such results are the Bishop-Phelps theorem [2] in 1963, a version of the Caristi-Brøndsted theorem [4,5] in 1976-1979, the Brøndsted theorem [3] in 1974, the multi-valued extension of the Caristi theorem due to

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Takahashi [28] in 1990, Nadler’s theorem [20] in 1969, Daneş theorem [8] in 1972, a supporting drops theorem, and applications to critical point theory including the Ekeland variational principle [11,12] in 1972-74.

On the other hand, since the appearances of the Ekeland variational principle [11, 12] in 1972-74 and the Caristi fixed point theorem [6] in 1976, hundreds of works followed on their equivalents, generalizations, applications, and related topics. Many of them are related to new spaces extending complete metric spaces, new metrics or topologies on them, and new order relations extending the so-called Caristi order.

While the author was working on such subjects in 1985-2000, we found a Metatheorem on ordered fixed point theory. It claims that certain order theoretic maximality statements are equivalent to theorems on fixed points, stationary points, common fixed points, common stationary points of families of maps or multimaps.

Recall that Brøndsted [3] in 1974 observed certain case that maximal elements are fixed points and that Jachymski [16] in 2003 studied when periodic points are same to fixed points. Recently, in 2022, we obtained a very useful result called the Brøndsted-Jachymski principle [25] combining their works and an extended version of our Metatheorem in [22-26] .

Motivated by these, in the present article, we obtain characterization of the order-theoretic version of the Cantor theorem due to Jachymski [17] in 2011 and the Caristi type theorem due to Granas-Horvath [14], that is, their equivalent formulations to maximality theorem, various types of collectively fixed point theorems and collectively stationary point theorems.

This article is organized as follows: Section 2 is to introduce the order-theoretic Cantor theorem due to Granas-Horvath ([14], Theorem 1). In Section 3, we introduce our 2023 Metatheorem and the Brøndsted-Jachymski principle as preliminaries. Sections 4 and 5 are for the equivalent formulations of Zorn’s Lemma and the order-theoretic Cantor theorem improved by Jachymski [17] in 2011, respectively. In Section 6, we introduce the Caristi type theorem for multimaps due to Granas-Horvath ([14], Theorem 3) and their equivalent formulations. Section 7 devotes to some information from other sources. Finally, Section 8 is for some conclusion.

2. Order-theoretic Cantor Theorem

We follow Granas and Horvath [14] in this section:

Let (X, \preceq) be a partially ordered set. For any $z \in X$, denote the (*terminal*) *tail* $\{y \in X : z \preceq y\}$ by Tz ; if $y \in Tz$, the set $Ty \subset Tz$ is called a *subtail* of Tz . Clearly an element y is maximal in (X, \preceq) provided $\{y\} = Ty$. A map $f : X \rightarrow X$ is said to be *expanding* or *progressive* if $x \preceq f(x)$ for each $x \in X$. We observe that if $f : X \rightarrow X$ is progressive then: (i) any tail in (X, \preceq) is invariant under f , (ii) any maximal element of (X, \preceq) is a fixed point of f .

Let $(X; d, \preceq)$ be a metric space in which a partial order \preceq is defined. We say that (X, d, \preceq) admits *arbitrarily small tails* if for each tail Tz and any $\varepsilon > 0$ there exists a subtail $Ty \subset Tz$ with $\text{diam}(Ty) \leq \varepsilon$.

Proposition 1. ([14]) *Let $(X; d, \preceq)$ be a partially ordered complete metric space which admits arbitrarily small tails. Then for any $x_0 \in X$ there exists an ascending and convergent sequence $x_0 \preceq x_1 \preceq \dots \preceq x_n \preceq \dots$ such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} x_n \in \bigcap_{n \in \mathbb{N}} \overline{Tx_n}$.*

Proposition 2. ([14]) *Let $(X; d, \preceq)$ be a partially ordered complete metric space which admits arbitrarily small tails and $f : X \rightarrow X$ an expanding continuous map. Then for each $x_0 \in X$ there exists a fixed point $\hat{x} = f(\hat{x})$ of f with $\hat{x} \in \overline{Tx_0}$.*

We now come to our main concept.

Definition. ([14]) We say that $(X; d, \preceq)$ is a *partially ordered Cantor space* (or simply a *Cantor space*), provided (i) tails are closed, (ii) $(X; d, \preceq)$ admits arbitrarily small tails and (iii) d is complete.

The following main property of Cantor spaces is given in [14] from Propositions 1 and 2:

Theorem 1. (Order-theoretic Cantor theorem) *Let $X = (X; d, \preceq)$ be a Cantor space. Then :*

(a) *Any tail Tx in X is also a Cantor space.*

- (b) X contains at least one maximal element.
- (c) Any tail Tx in X contains at least one maximal element x^* in X .
- (d) If $f : X \rightarrow X$ is expanding, then each tail Tx contains a fixed point of f .

One of our aim in this article is to generalize this theorem.

3. Metatheorem in Ordered Fixed Point Theory

We introduce the 2023 Metatheorem, a new version of the one in [26]:

Metatheorem. *Let X be a set, A its nonempty subset, and $G(x, y)$ a sentence formula for $x, y \in X$. Then the following are equivalent:*

- (α) *There exists an element $v \in A$ such that $G(v, w)$ for any $w \in X \setminus \{v\}$.*
- ($\beta 1$) *If $f : A \rightarrow X$ is a map such that for any $x \in A$ with $x \neq f(x)$, there exists a $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $\neg G(x, y)$, then f has a fixed element $v \in A$, that is, $v = f(v)$.*
- ($\beta 2$) *If \mathfrak{F} is a family of maps $f : A \rightarrow X$ such that for any $x \in A$ with $x \neq f(x)$, there exists a $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $\neg G(x, y)$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in A$, that is, $v = f(v)$ for all $f \in \mathfrak{F}$.*
- ($\gamma 1$) *If $f : A \rightarrow X$ is a map such that $\neg G(x, f(x))$ for any $x \in A$, then f has a fixed element $v \in A$, that is, $v = f(v)$.*
- ($\gamma 2$) *If \mathfrak{F} is a family of maps $f : A \rightarrow X$ satisfying $\neg G(x, f(x))$ for all $x \in A$ with $x \neq f(x)$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in A$, that is, $v = f(v)$ for all $f \in \mathfrak{F}$.*
- ($\delta 1$) *If $F : A \multimap X$ is a multimap such that, for any $x \in A \setminus F(x)$ there exists $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $\neg G(x, y)$, then F has a fixed element $v \in A$, that is, $v \in F(v)$.*
- ($\delta 2$) *Let \mathfrak{F} be a family of multimaps $F : A \multimap X$ such that, for any $x \in A \setminus F(x)$ there exists $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $\neg G(x, y)$. Then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in A$, that is, $v \in F(v)$ for all $F \in \mathfrak{F}$.*
- ($\epsilon 1$) *If $F : A \multimap X$ is a multimap satisfying $\neg G(x, y)$ for any $x \in A$ and any $y \in F(x) \setminus \{x\}$, then F has a stationary element $v \in A$, that is, $\{v\} = F(v)$.*
- ($\epsilon 2$) *If \mathfrak{F} is a family of multimaps $F : A \multimap X$ such that $\neg G(x, y)$ holds for any $x \in A$ and any $y \in F(x) \setminus \{x\}$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common stationary element $v \in A$, that is, $\{v\} = F(v)$ for all $F \in \mathfrak{F}$.*
- (η) *If Y is a subset of X such that for each $x \in A \setminus Y$ there exists a $z \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $\neg G(x, z)$, then there exists a $v \in A \cap Y$.*

Here, \neg denotes the negation. For the proof, see Park [25, 26].

This Metatheorem guarantees the truth of all items when one of them is true. Since 1985, we have shown nearly one hundred cases of such situation; see [22-26].

For an ordered set (X, \preceq) and a map $f : X \rightarrow X$, we define

- $\text{Max}(\preceq)$: the set of maximal elements;
- $\text{Fix}(f)$: the set of fixed points of f ;
- $\text{Per}(f)$: the set of periodic points $x \in X$; that is, $x = f^n(x)$ for some $n \in \mathbb{N}$.

In our previous work [25], we introduced the following:

Brøndsted-Jachymski Principle. *Let (X, \preceq) be a partially ordered set and $f : X \rightarrow X$ be a progressive map. Then a maximal element $v \in X$ is a fixed and periodic point of f , that is,*

$$\text{Max}(\preceq) \subset \text{Fix}(f) = \text{Per}(f).$$

This is not claiming the non-emptiness of the three sets.

4. Equivalents of Zorn’s Lemma

The Axiom of Choice has the following equivalent form:

Zorn’s Lemma. *A partially ordered set in which every totally ordered subset has an upper bound contains at least one maximal element.*

As the first application of the Brøndsted-Jachymski Principle, we improved Zermelo’s fixed point theorem implicitly given in [30] as follows [25]:

Theorem 2. *Let (X, \preceq) be a partially ordered set in which each nonempty well-ordered subset has a supremum (least upper bound). Then every progressive map $f : X \rightarrow X$ has*

$$\text{Fix}(f) = \text{Per}(f) \supset \text{Max}(\preceq) \neq \emptyset.$$

Jachymski [15] noted: “Under the Axiom of Choice, the assumption of Theorem 2 can be weakened to “each nonempty well-ordered subset has an upper bound.” This improves Kneser’s [19] fixed point theorem, which turns out to be equivalent to the Axiom of Choice as shown by Abian [1].”

However we have the following particular form of our Metatheorem in [23–26]:

Theorem 3. *Let (X, \preceq) be a partially ordered set, $x_0 \in X$, let the tail $A = T(x_0) = \{y \in X : x_0 \preceq y\}$ has an upper bound.*

Then the following six equivalent statements hold:

(α) *There exists a maximal (resp. minimal) element $v \in A$ such that $v \not\preceq w$ (resp. $w \not\preceq v$) for any $w \in X \setminus \{v\}$.*

(β) *If \mathfrak{F} is a family of maps $f : A \rightarrow X$ such that for any $x \in A$ with $x \neq f(x)$, there exists a $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $x \preceq y$ (resp. $y \preceq x$), then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in A$, that is, $v = f(v)$ for all $f \in \mathfrak{F}$.*

(γ) *If \mathfrak{F} is a family of maps $f : A \rightarrow X$ satisfying $x \preceq f(x)$ (resp. $f(x) \preceq x$) for all $x \in A$ with $x \neq f(x)$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in A$, that is, $v = f(v)$ for all $f \in \mathfrak{F}$.*

(δ) *Let \mathfrak{F} be a family of multimaps $F : A \multimap X$ such that, for any $x \in A \setminus F(x)$ there exists $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $x \preceq y$ (resp. $y \preceq x$). Then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in A$, that is, $v \in F(v)$ for all $F \in \mathfrak{F}$.*

(ϵ) *If \mathfrak{F} is a family of multimaps $F : A \multimap X$ such that $x \preceq y$ (resp. $y \preceq x$) holds for any $x \in A$ and any $y \in F(x) \setminus \{x\}$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common stationary element $v \in A$, that is, $\{v\} = F(v)$ for all $F \in \mathfrak{F}$.*

(η) *If Y is a subset of X such that for each $x \in A \setminus Y$ there exists a $z \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $x \preceq z$ (resp. $z \preceq x$), then there exists a $v \in A \cap Y$.*

Proof. (α) Since A has an upper bound $v \in A$, for each $x \in A$, we have $x_0 \preceq x \preceq v$. If $v \preceq w$ for some $w \in X$, then $w \in T(x_0) = A$ and $w \preceq v$. Since (X, \preceq) is partially ordered, we have $w = v$. Hence v is maximal.

The equivalency (α)–(η) follows from our Metatheorem. \square

When \mathfrak{F} is a singleton, (β)–(ϵ) are denoted by ($\beta 1$)–($\epsilon 1$), respectively, as in the Metatheorem. Note that ($\gamma 1$) improves Zermelo’s fixed point theorem. Moreover, (α) implies the following extension of Zorn’s Lemma:

Theorem 4. *Let (X, \preceq) be a partially ordered set, $x_0 \in X$, let the tail $A = T(x_0) = \{y \in X : x_0 \preceq y\}$ has an upper bound $v \in A$. Then v is a maximal element of (X, \preceq) . Moreover, if $f : A \rightarrow X$ is progressive, then we have*

$$\text{Fix}(f) = \text{Per}(f) \supset \text{Max}(\preceq) \neq \emptyset.$$

5. Extensions of Order-theoretic Cantor Theorem

In 2011, Jachymski [17] obtained a stationary point theorem characterizing metric completeness as follows:

Theorem 5. ([17]) *Let (X, d) be a metric space and $\text{Cl}(X)$ the family of all nonempty closed subsets of X . Then the following statements are equivalent:*

- (a) (X, d) is complete.
- (b) For any multimap $F : X \rightarrow \text{Cl}(X)$ such that, for every $x \in X$, (1) $F(Fx) \subseteq Fx$, and (2) for any $\varepsilon > 0$, there exists $y \in Fx$ such that $\text{diam } Fy < \varepsilon$, F has a stationary point.
- (c) For any multimap $F : X \rightarrow \text{Cl}(X)$ satisfying (1) and (2), F has a fixed point.

From Theorem 5, Jachymski obtained a particular form ([17], Theorem 2) of the Ekeland principle and the following form ([17], Theorem 3) of the order-theoretic Cantor theorem due to Granas-Horvath [14] and Granas-Dugundji ([13], p.32–33).

Theorem 6. ([17]) *Let (X, d) be a complete metric space endowed with a partial order \preceq . Assume that for any $x \in X$, the set $Tx = \{y \in X : x \preceq y\}$ is closed and given $\varepsilon > 0$, there is $y \in X$ satisfying $x \preceq y$ and $\text{diam } Ty < \varepsilon$. Then*

- (α) (X, \preceq) has a maximal element.

Combining Theorems 3 and 6, we obtain the following equivalent formulations:

Theorem 7. *Let (X, \preceq) be a partially ordered complete metric space, $x_0 \in X$, let the tail $A = T(x_0) = \{y \in X : x_0 \preceq y\}$ closed and given $\varepsilon > 0$, there is $y \in X$ satisfying $x_0 \preceq y$ and $\text{diam } Ty < \varepsilon$.*

Then the six equivalent statements in Theorem 3.(α)–(η) hold including

- (α) X has a maximal element $v \in A$, that is, $v \not\prec w$ for any $w \in X \setminus \{v\}$.

For a Cantor space, Theorem 7 contains Theorem 1(b),(c),(d).

Moreover, from Theorems 1 or 7(i) and the Brøndsted-Jachymski Principle, we have the following:

Theorem 8. *Let $(X; d, \preceq)$ be a Cantor space and $f : X \rightarrow X$ be a progressive map. Then we have*

$$\text{Fix}(f) = \text{Per}(f) \supset \text{Max}(\preceq) \neq \emptyset.$$

6. Equivalent formulations of the Caristi theorem

In this section, we are interested on the following in Granas-Horvath ([14], Theorem 3):

Theorem 9. ([14]) *Let (X, d) be a complete metric space endowed with a partial order \preceq and $\varphi : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ be a lower semicontinuous function on X . Then given any $x_0 \in X$, there exists an x^* such that $x_0 \preceq_\varphi x^*$ such that x^* is a common fixed point for the family of maps (not necessarily continuous) $f : X \rightarrow X$ for which Caristi’s condition holds.*

Here Caristi’s condition means:

$$x \preceq f(x) \text{ iff } d(x, f(x)) \leq \varphi(x) - \varphi(f(x)) \text{ for } x \in X.$$

We give equivalent formulations of Theorem 9 as follows:

Theorem 10. *Let (X, \preceq) be a partially ordered complete metric space, and a function $\varphi : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ be lower semicontinuous such that*

$$x \preceq y \text{ iff } d(x, y) \leq \varphi(x) - \varphi(y) \text{ for } x, y \in X.$$

Let $x_0 \in X$ and $A = T(x_0)$. Then the following six equivalent statements hold:

- (α) There exists a maximal element $v \in A$; that is, $v \not\preceq w$ for any $w \in X \setminus \{v\}$, that is, $Tv = \{v\}$.
- (β) If \mathfrak{F} is a family of maps $f : A \rightarrow X$ such that for any $x \in A$ with $x \neq f(x)$, there exists a $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $x \preceq y$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in A$, that is, $v = f(v)$ for all $f \in \mathfrak{F}$.
- (γ) If \mathfrak{F} is a family of maps $f : A \rightarrow X$ satisfying $x \preceq f(x)$ for all $x \in A$ with $x \neq f(x)$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in A$, that is, $v = f(v)$ for all $f \in \mathfrak{F}$.
- (δ) Let \mathfrak{F} be a family of multimaps $F : A \multimap X$ such that, for any $x \in A \setminus F(x)$ there exists $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $x \preceq y$. Then \mathfrak{F} has a common fixed element $v \in A$, that is, $v \in F(v)$ for all $F \in \mathfrak{F}$.
- (ϵ) If \mathfrak{F} is a family of multimaps $F : A \multimap X$ such that $x \preceq y$ holds for any $x \in A$ and any $y \in F(x) \setminus \{x\}$, then \mathfrak{F} has a common stationary element $v \in A$, that is, $\{v\} = F(v)$ for all $F \in \mathfrak{F}$.
- (η) Let \mathcal{F} be a family of multimaps $F : A \multimap X$ such that, for all $x \in A$ with $F(x) \neq \emptyset$, there exists $y \in X \setminus \{x\}$ satisfying $x \preceq y$. Then there exists $v \in A$ such that $F(v) = \emptyset$ for all $T \in \mathcal{F}$.

Note that (γ 1) is just Theorem 9 and the others are its equivalent formulations. Moreover, (β 1) improves the Caristi theorem.

Moreover, from Theorems 9 or 10(α) and the Brøndsted-Jachymski Principle, we have the following:

Theorem 11. Let $(X; d, \preceq)$ be a partially ordered complete metric space, and a function $\varphi : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ be lower semicontinuous such that

$$x \preceq y \text{ iff } d(x, y) \leq \varphi(x) - \varphi(y) \text{ for } x, y \in X$$

and $f : X \rightarrow X$ be a progressive map. Then we have

$$\text{Fix}(f) = \text{Per}(f) \supset \text{Max}(\preceq) \neq \emptyset.$$

This improves the Caristi fixed point theorem.

7. Comments on Some Related Works

In this section we introduce “abstracts” or certain comments on some works related to Granas-Horvath [14] not mentioned in the previous sections.

(I) W.S. DU [9] (2008): “By applying an abstract maximal element principle (MEP) by Lin and Du, we obtain a generalized Brézis-Browder principle, system (vectorial) versions of Ekeland’s variational principle and maximal element principle and a vectorial version of Takahashi’s nonconvex minimization theorem. Moreover, we investigate the equivalence between scalar versions and vectorial versions of these results.”

“In 2000, Granas and Horvath [14] first studied on a so-called Cantor space and obtained some fixed point theorems and MEP.”

(II) M. PĂCURAR, I.A. RUS [21] (2011): “By various examples we illustrate that the ordered set theory is far away from having unitary notations and terminology. Some suggestions for unifying the terminology are also presented.”

In this paper, it is pointed that three theorems due to Turinici [29] in 1982, Dancs-Hegedüs-Medvegyev [7] in 1983, and Granas-Horvath ([14], Theorem 1) in 2000 are actually the same, but expressed each in a different language.

(III) J. JACHYMSKI, J. KLIMA [18] in 2016: “ We establish an extension of Cantor’s intersection theorem for a K -metric space (X, d) , where d is a generalized metric taking values in a solid cone K in a Banach space E . This generalizes a recent result of Alnafe'i, Radenović and Shahzad in 2011 obtained for a K -metric

space over a solid strongly minihedral cone. Next we show that our Cantor's theorem yields a special case of a generalization of Banach's contraction principle given very recently by Cvetković and Rakočević in 2014. ... ”

(IV) L. PASICKI [27] in 2016: “The paper is mainly devoted to fixed point theorems. More general versions of important theorems of Matkowski, Romaguera, Takahashi, Brøndsted, and Banach are proved. Also, Ekeland's variational principle is extended. On the way to the main results, short proofs of crucial properties of partial metric spaces are proposed. In addition, the notion of kernel of partial metric is suggested together with a standard method of proving fixed point theorems. We also supply a useful criterion for Cauchy sequences.”

8. Conclusion

In this paper, we have obtained extended versions of classical theorems of Zermelo, Cantor, Zorn, and Caristi and their equivalent formulations based on our Metatheorem and the Brøndsted-Jachymski principle recently due to ourselves.

As we have seen Metatheorem and its applications in [22–26], we showed that the existence of maximal elements in certain preordered sets implies that of fixed points or stationary points of maps or multimaps and to common fixed points or common stationary points of a family of maps or multimaps. Therefore, if we have a theorem on existence of maximal points, it can be converted to at least eight equivalent theorems on other types of points without any serious argument.

In many fields of mathematical sciences, there are plentiful number of theorems concerning maximal points or various fixed points that can be applicable our Metatheorem in [22–26]. Some of such theorems can be seen in our previous works and the present article. Therefore, our Metatheorem is a machine to expand our knowledge easily. In this article we presented relatively old and well-known examples.

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